

**MACHINE LEARNING – BASED PREDICTION OF VITAMIN DEFICIENCY
DISEASES AND PERSONALIZED FOOD RECOMMENDATIONS****Dr. M. Dhanalakshmi**Professor of IT, Department of Information Technology,
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dhana.miryala@jntuh.ac.in**S. Sai Lakshmi Tanmai**MCA Student, Department of Information Technology,
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tanmaisatyavolu@gmail.com**ABSTRACT**

A machine learning-based system that employs several algorithms to analyse personal health data, detect vitamin deficiencies, and forecast related illnesses is suggested as a solution to these problems. To guarantee accurate disease prediction, the most accurate model is used. Additionally, the system makes use of extensive nutritional databases to suggest meals high in vitamins based on the user's dietary requirements and interests. This technique attempts to improve general well-being and encourage the adoption of balanced, nutrient-dense eating habits by providing individualized dietary and health advice.

Keywords:

Disease Prediction, machine learning, vitamin, nutritional values, classification models.

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the rise in lifestyle-related diseases and nutritional deficiencies has become a major global health concern. Poor dietary habits—particularly the increasing reliance on fast food—have led to an alarming surge in vitamin and mineral deficiencies, contributing to chronic conditions such as hypertension, cardiovascular diseases, and various forms of cancer.

To address this issue, the proposed system operates within a Machine Learning (ML) environment, utilizing multiple ML algorithms to detect vitamin deficiencies and predict potential diseases associated with them. The system evaluates the accuracy of each model and selects the best-performing one for precise prediction. It analyses an individual's health and dietary data to provide personalized disease predictions and food recommendations. Moreover, it integrates comprehensive nutritional databases to suggest vitamin-rich food items, aligning with the individual's dietary preferences and restrictions.

LITERATURE SURVEY**• Statistical Models' Performance in Predicting Vitamin D Levels**

Authors: S. Bechroui, A. Monir, H. Mraoui, E. H. Sebbar, E. Saalaoui, and M. Choukri

Abstract: This study investigates the performance of various statistical models in predicting vitamin D levels based on demographic, clinical, and environmental factors. The research focuses on understanding the correlation between key features and vitamin D concentration in individuals, aiming to provide an effective predictive approach.

• A Decision Tree Model for Assessing Vitamin D Deficiency Risk Factors

Authors: K. Gonoodi, M. Tayefi, M. Saberi-Karimian, A. A. Zadeh, S. Darroudi, S. K. Farahmand, Z. Abasalti, A. Moslem, M. Nematy, G. A. Ferns, S. Eslami, and M. G. Mobarhan

Abstract: This study focuses on identifying and analyzing the risk components contributing to vitamin D deficiency. It employs a model to classify, predict individuals at risk, providing a data-driven framework to understand the relationships between various demographic, lifestyle, and clinical parameters and vitamin D levels.

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- **Comparing Clinical Event Prediction Machine Learning Algorithms**

Authors: J.-J. Beunza, E. Puertas, E. García-Ovejero, G. Villalba, E. Condes, G. Koleva, C. Hurtado, and M. F. Landecho

Abstract: This study evaluates and compares the performance of different machine learning algorithms for predicting the risk of coronary heart disease (CHD).

- **Vitamin D, cognition, and dementia: a systematic review and meta-analysis.**

Authors: A. Kuwabara, N. Tsugawa, K. Mizuno, H. Ogasawara, Y. Watanabe, and K. Tanaka

Abstract: This study introduces the Vitamin D Deficiency Questionnaire for Japanese adults (VDDQ-J), a simple tool designed to predict the likelihood of vitamin D deficiency. The questionnaire incorporates factors such as lifestyle, dietary habits, and sun exposure specific to the Japanese population.

- **Developing and Validating Machine Learning Algorithms and Applying Rule-Based Algorithms to Locate Patients with Lupus in Electronic Health Records**

Authors: A. Jorge, V. M. Castro, A. Barnado, V. Gainer, C. Hong, T. Cai, R. Carroll, J. C. Denny, L. Crofford, K. H. Costenbader, K. P. Liao, E. W. Karlson, and C. H. Feldman

Abstract: This study focuses on developing and validating machine learning and rule-based algorithms to identify systemic lupus erythematosus (SLE) patients from electronic health records (EHR).

EXISTING SYSTEM

Two food recommender systems are discussed: one uses user preferences and ingredient matching to suggest recipes, but lacks nutritional balance and variety; the other, an Android-based system, uses tags, latent factors, and matrix factorization for personalized recommendations, but also ignores dietary nutrition needs.

Disadvantages of existing system:

- Current diet guidance systems frequently emphasize maintaining balanced food patterns or addressing particular ailments.
- For disease-specific recommendations, these systems suggest foods without considering the severity of the condition, which can vary between patients and potentially lead to harmful effects.
- Likewise, in diet-balancing recommendations, essential nutritional factors are often overlooked, even though they play a crucial role in creating effective and healthy diet plans.

PROPOSED SYSTEM

The system operates within a Machine Learning environment, utilizing multiple algorithms to evaluate the accuracy of vitamin deficiency detection and food recommendation. The most accurate model is selected and integrated into a Flask-based web application for real-time predictions. When a user inputs their vitamin levels, the algorithm predicts potential deficiencies and suggests appropriate foods to address them.

The suggested system's benefits include:

- Automating the process of identifying vitamin deficiencies and recommending foods
- Training and testing are done using pre-existing datasets.
- The model's accuracy is higher than that of the current approaches.

METHODOLOGY

SYSTEM OUTLINE

Figure 1: Architecture diagram

- The graphic shows the flowchart of a web application that uses machine learning to diagnose vitamin deficiencies and recommend foods.
- The process starts with user registration or login, followed by inputting vitamin levels (A, B, C, D, E, K). A MySQL database has this data.
- The system suggests suitable foods using a food recommendation dataset and trains a machine learning model for diagnosing deficits using a vitamin dataset.
- The vitamin dataset is split and utilized for testing and training the model, which is saved in .pkl format. The model forecasts deficiencies and suggests appropriate foods based on user input.
- The entire process is integrated into a Flask web application for easy user interaction and real-time results.

ALGORITHMS

- **Support Vector Machine (SVM):** SVM's are widely utilized for tasks like regression, classification, and outlier detection. They perform well even when there are more features than samples, and they are especially good at handling high-dimensional datasets.
- **Random Forest:** By combining feature randomness and bootstrap aggregation, this algorithm builds an ensemble of uncorrelated decision trees, expanding on the classic bagging technique.
- **K-Nearest Neighbours (KNN):** Using a distance metric like the Manhattan, Minkowski, or Euclidean distance, predictions are generated by locating the k closest data points in the feature space. Regression predictions are based on the average of the neighbour's data, whereas the output for classification is decided by a majority vote among neighbours.
- **Decision Tree:** It is a hierarchical, tree-like architecture that consists of internal nodes, branches, leaf nodes, and a root node. The divide-and-conquer strategy is used to learn a decision tree, utilizing a greedy search strategy to identify the best split points at each step.
- **Voting Classifier:** Ensemble learning method that generates a final output by combining predictions from several base classifiers, often known as estimators.

CONCLUSION

This project demonstrates the transformative potential of machine learning in preventive healthcare by effectively identifying vitamin deficiencies and their associated health risks. Through personalized dietary recommendations and early disease prediction, the system empowers both individuals and

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healthcare providers to make informed, proactive health decisions. The integration of a user-friendly interface with advanced data analysis enhances accessibility and usability, ultimately contributing to improved public health outcomes and reduced medical costs. By leveraging AI for nutritional assessment, this project lays the groundwork for a more data-driven, efficient, and preventive approach to modern healthcare.

FUTURE SCOPE

- **Integration with Wearable Devices:** Connect with smartwatches, fitness bands, and health apps like Apple Health or Google Fit to gather real-time data.
- **Improved Prediction Accuracy:** Use additional real-time input to enhance deficiency and disease prediction accuracy.
- **Advanced Deep Learning Models:** Incorporate neural networks and LSTM models to analyze complex user data patterns.
- **Personalized Health Insights:** Provide more precise and detailed health analysis based on individual patterns.

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